

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

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Project title: Molecular mechanisms of tumorigenesis in primary aldosteronism

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2 Summary

German version

Primärer Aldosteronismus ist die häufigste hormonbedingte Ursache für Bluthochdruck. Er wird durch eine übermäßige Produktion des Hormons Aldosteron verursacht, das den Salzhaushalt, die Flüssigkeitsretention und den Blutdruck reguliert. Bei vielen Patientinnen und Patienten wird diese Erkrankung durch gutartige Tumoren in der Nebenniere verursacht (Aldosteron-produzierende Adenome, APAs), die häufig durch eine Operation geheilt werden können.

Ziel dieses Projekts war es, zu untersuchen, wie diese Tumoren entstehen und sich entwickeln. Wir kombinierten moderne molekulare Technologien (einschließlich räumlicher Transkriptomik und bildgebungsbasierter Metabolomik) mit funktionellen Laborexperimenten und klinischen Daten. Dadurch konnten wir nicht nur untersuchen, welche Gene aktiv sind, sondern auch, wo spezifische Prozesse im Gewebe stattfinden.

Wir konnten zeigen, dass Aldosteron-produzierende Mikronoduli mögliche Vorläuferläsionen von APAs darstellen. Ein zentrales Ergebnis war die Identifizierung eines Markers (ABCC3), der normale hormonproduzierende Zellen von frühen Krankheitsstadien unterscheidet und damit eine verbesserte Erkennung der Tumorentstehung ermöglicht.

Die Studie zeigte außerdem, dass Tumorzellen umfassende metabolische Anpassungen durchlaufen, um zu überleben. Insbesondere schützen sie sich vor oxidativem Stress, einer Form zellulärer Schädigung, indem sie ihren Stoffwechsel umprogrammieren. Dieser Prozess, der mit einer Form des Zelltods namens Ferroptose verbunden ist, spielt eine zentrale Rolle für das Tumorwachstum. Wir identifizierten spezifische Gene, darunter *BEX1* und *EGR1*, die das Gleichgewicht zwischen Hormonproduktion, Stressantworten und Zellüberleben regulieren.

Wir fanden, dass verschiedene genetische Subtypen dieser Tumoren unterschiedlichen biologischen Signalwegen folgen. Einige Tumoren passen sich an oxidativen Stress an, indem sie widerstandsfähiger werden, während andere schützende antioxidative Mechanismen entwickeln. Diese Unterschiede können zur phänotypischen Variabilität beitragen, die zwischen Tumoren unterschiedlicher Genotypen beobachtet wird.

Abschließend konnten wir durch die Integration molekularer Befunde mit klinischen Daten zeigen, dass die Nebennieren-Histopathologie (die mikroskopische Struktur des chirurgisch entfernten Gewebes) ein zentraler Prädiktor für den Patientenerfolg nach der Operation ist. Dies unterstreicht die Bedeutung einer detaillierten Gewebeanalyse für die Steuerung des Langzeitmanagements.

Insgesamt liefert dieses Projekt neue Einblicke in die Entwicklung hormonproduzierender Nebennierentumoren und verknüpft zugrunde liegende biologische Mechanismen mit klinischen Ergebnissen. Diese Erkenntnisse können eine verbesserte Diagnostik, Risikostratifizierung und die Entwicklung präziserer Therapien für Patientinnen und Patienten mit primärem Aldosteronismus unterstützen.

English version

Primary aldosteronism is the most common hormone-related cause of high blood pressure. It is driven by excessive production of the hormone aldosterone, which regulates salt balance, fluid retention, and blood pressure. In many patients, this condition is caused by benign tumours in the adrenal gland (aldosterone-producing adenomas, APAs), which can often be cured by surgery.

This project aimed to investigate how these tumours form and evolve. We combined advanced molecular technologies (including spatial transcriptomics and imaging-based metabolomics) with functional laboratory experiments and clinical data. This allowed us to study not only which genes are active, but also where specific processes occur within the tissue.

We showed that aldosterone-producing micronodules may represent precursor lesions to APAs. A key finding was the identification of a marker (*ABCC3*) that distinguishes normal hormone-producing cells from early disease stages, enabling improved detection of tumour initiation.

The study also revealed that tumour cells undergo major metabolic adaptations to survive. In particular, they protect themselves from oxidative stress, a form of cellular damage, by reprogramming their metabolism. This process, linked to a form of cell death called ferroptosis, plays a central role in tumour growth. We identified specific genes, including *BEX1* and *EGR1*, that regulate the balance between hormone production, stress responses and cell survival.

We found that different genetic subtypes of these tumours follow distinct biological pathways. Some tumours adapt to oxidative stress by becoming more resistant, while others develop protective antioxidant mechanisms. These differences may contribute to the phenotypic variability observed between tumours of different genotypes.

Finally, by integrating molecular findings with clinical data, we demonstrated that adrenal histopathology (the microscopic structure of the surgically removed tissue) is a key predictor of patient outcomes after surgery. This highlights the importance of detailed tissue analysis for guiding long-term management.

Overall, this project provides new insight into how hormone-producing adrenal tumours develop, linking underlying biological mechanisms to clinical outcomes. These findings may support improved diagnosis, risk stratification and the development of more precise treatments for patients with primary aldosteronism.

3 Progress Report

The project successfully delivered a coherent set of findings across 9 original research publications (published project results, **section 4.1**), collectively fulfilling research aims and advancing translational understanding of PA.

3.1. Functional mechanisms of aldosterone production and cell survival (Aim 1)

Tetraspanin 12 (TSPAN12) was characterised as a negative regulator of aldosterone production (**original research publication #1**). In a cohort of 30 APAs, *TSPAN12* expression levels showed a significant inverse correlation with baseline plasma aldosterone concentrations ($R = -0.47$; $P = 0.009$). Angiotensin II (Ang II) stimulation (10 nM for 6 hours) induced a 1.6-fold (± 0.13) increase in *TSPAN12* expression via Ca^{2+} /calmodulin signalling, an effect abolished by nifedipine ($P = 0.0097$) or W-7 ($P = 0.0022$). Functional assays demonstrated that *TSPAN12* knockdown increases aldosterone production under both basal and Ang II-stimulated conditions. In pig models with low-salt diets, TSPAN12 was markedly increased in the zona glomerulosa (ZG), supporting its role as an aldosterone suppressor

3.1.2. Brain-expressed X-linked protein 1 (BEX1) was shown to protect adrenal cells from ferroptosis, supporting tumour cell survival under oxidative stress (**original research publication #2**). *BEX1* was significantly upregulated in micro-APAs (<10 mm diameter) compared to macro-APAs (≥ 10 mm diameter), with a 2.76-fold increase ($P < 0.001$), and a 3.85-fold increase compared to paired adrenal cortex ($P < 0.05$). In the No Mutation Detected (NMD) group, *BEX1* expression showed a linear negative correlation with APA diameter ($r = -0.501$, $P = 0.007$). Functional studies demonstrated that stable *BEX1* expression did not alter cell cycle progression or apoptosis but conferred significant protection against cell death by ferroptosis ($P < 0.01$), as measured by flow cytometry, indicating its role in promoting cell survival in adrenal tumours

3.1.3. ATPase sarcoplasmic/endoplasmic reticulum Ca^{2+} transporting 3 (ATP2A3) was identified through machine learning as a key feature gene in APAs and validated as a promoter of aldosterone production via calcium handling (**original research publication #3**). Spatial transcriptomics confirmed its upregulation in APAs compared to adjacent cortex. In human adrenocortical cells, Ang II treatment increased *ATP2A3* expression 9.15-fold. Silencing *ATP2A3* decreased basal *CYP11B2* (aldosterone synthase) expression and aldosterone secretion by 3.51-fold and 1.46-fold, respectively, and by 1.77-fold and 1.94-fold under Ang II stimulation. Dietary sodium restriction in pigs significantly increased *ATP2A3* levels, and spatial transcriptomics showed APA cells exhibited the highest *ATP2A3* expression among all adrenal cell types. The suppressive effect of *ATP2A3* silencing on *CYP11B2* was enhanced by calcium inhibitors.

3.1.4. Early Growth Response 1 (EGR1) was identified as a central node linking redox balance to aldosterone biosynthesis (**original research publication #4**). Integrated analysis of ferroptosis-related RNA sequencing and spatial transcriptomics demonstrated that *EGR1* silencing in adrenal cells reduces oxidative stress while increasing *CYP11B2* gene expression and aldosterone production, whereas its overexpression produces the opposite effect. Notably, *EGR1* expression was downregulated in APAs and aldosterone-producing micronodules (APMs) compared to the adjacent adrenal cortex, correlating with decreased levels of oxidative stress markers. These findings were corroborated in pig adrenals with

secondary hyperaldosteronism, revealing a novel mechanism connecting EGR1 to oxidative stress regulation and steroidogenesis.

Together, these findings elucidate critical mechanisms governing aldosterone production and adrenal cell survival, providing new insights into PA pathophysiology.

3.2. Zonation biology and diagnostic markers; genotype–phenotype links (Aim 2; supports Aim 3)

ATP Binding Cassette Subfamily C Member 3 (ABCC3) was identified as a novel and practical marker to distinguish normal ZG from aldosterone-producing lesions (**original research publication #5**). A marked reduction in ABCC3 was observed in APAs and APMs compared to the adjacent adrenal cortex, cortisol-producing adenomas, and non-functioning adenomas. Crucially, spatial transcriptomics and immunofluorescence revealed a precise inverse expression pattern between ABCC3 and CYP11B2; high ABCC3 expression was exclusively found in CYP11B2-negative ZG cells. This distinguishes it from common ZG markers like KCNJ5, which are expressed in both normal and neoplastic cells. The reduction in APAs showed genotypic variability: APAs harbouring KCNJ5 mutations exhibited significantly higher residual ABCC3 mRNA and protein levels than their KCNJ5 wild-type (KCNJ5^{WT}) counterparts. Functional validation in human adrenocortical cells confirmed that both angiotensin II stimulation and induced expression of the KCNJ5-L168R mutation upregulated CYP11B2 transcription while simultaneously suppressing ABCC3 expression. This establishes ABCC3 as a histological tool for delineating normal zonation from pathological aldosterone-producing tissue.

Integrated multi-omics analyses revealed marked genotype-dependent metabolic states and transcriptional programmes that underpin APA pathophysiology. Spatial transcriptomics of APA specimens identified two conserved transcriptional profiles within CYP11B2-positive regions. A ‘ZG-like’ signature (CYP11B2-type 1) was prevalent in KCNJ5^{WT}-APAs, while a ‘zona fasciculata/reticularis-like’ signature (CYP11B2-type 2) was predominant in KCNJ5-mutant APAs. This transcriptional heterogeneity was mirrored by distinct metabolomic profiles. KCNJ5^{WT}-APAs accumulated pro-oxidant metabolites that promote oxidative stress and cell death. In contrast, KCNJ5-mutant APAs were characterised by a significant enrichment of antioxidant metabolites, which supports their observed lipid-rich clear cell morphology and greater expansion-prone phenotype (**original research publication #6**).

Bulk transcriptomic analyses further demonstrated an APA-wide metabolic reprogramming towards PPAR α -driven fatty acid β -oxidation and glycolysis, coupled with enhanced antioxidant defences. This reprogramming was associated with an immunosuppressive tumour microenvironment, evidenced by a substantial 3.45-fold reduction in CD45+ immune cell infiltration in APAs compared to the adjacent adrenal cortex ($p < 0.001$). The association of heightened lipid metabolism with both ferroptosis resistance and antioxidant upregulation suggests a key survival advantage for APA tumour cells (**original research publication #7**).

3.3. APM-to-APA transition and precursor states (Aim 3)

Our spatial transcriptomic data have revealed the existence of APA-like cell subpopulations within the histologically normal adrenal cortex adjacent to resected tumours (**original research publication #6**). Crucially, these subpopulations lack CYP11B2 gene expression, identifying them not as active aldosterone-producing cells but as putative precursor niches.

This discovery provided first direct molecular evidence for the multi-step progression from a precursor state to a clinical APA, a process long hypothesised in adrenocortical tumourigenesis.

3.4. Clinical phenotype, histopathology, and outcomes (Aim 2; translational goal)

A prospective, single-centre study provided critical insights into the relationship between adrenal histopathology and short-term post-surgical outcomes using the PASO (Primary Aldosteronism Surgical Outcome) and HISTALDO (HISTopathology of primary ALDOsteronism) criteria to assess postsurgical outcomes and adrenal histopathology, respectively (**original research publication #8**).

The cohort of 60 consecutively operated patients revealed a significant distinction between classical and nonclassical histopathological findings. The classical group (n=45), characterised by a solitary APA or dominant nodule, presented with a more severe biochemical phenotype at baseline, exhibiting significantly higher plasma aldosterone concentrations (262 pg/mL *versus* 155 pg/mL, $P=0.008$) and aldosterone-to-renin ratios ($P=0.002$) compared to the nonclassical group (n=15), which comprised cases of multiple APAs or diffuse hyperplasia. This divergence was starkly reflected in surgical outcomes.

The classical group achieved a markedly higher incidence of complete biochemical success at short-term follow-up (97.6%) compared to the nonclassical group (66.7%, $P=0.002$). Adrenal vein sampling data showed an increased ratio of absolute aldosterone concentration in the contralateral adrenal vein to the peripheral vein in the nonclassical group ($P=0.004$), indicating a higher incidence of inappropriate aldosterone production from the unresected gland.

Notably, while aldosterone-driver gene mutations were identified in 85% of APAs, the *KCNJ5* mutation status did not stratify short-term clinical or biochemical outcomes within the classical solitary APA group, highlighting the primacy of histopathology over genotype for short-term prognostic stratification.

A long-term follow-up study with extended follow-up to a median of 89 months, unveiled a significant and previously underappreciated risk of biochemical disease recurrence despite short-term disease remission. In the 57 patients with available long-term data, short-term assessment at 12 months showed a 93% rate of complete biochemical success (43 classical and 10 nonclassical cases). However, long-term evaluation demonstrated biochemical recurrence of PA in 23% (12/53) of these initially successful cases.

This recurrence was overwhelmingly associated with nonclassical histopathology; 60% (6/10) of patients with nonclassical histopathology experienced recurrence, compared to only 14% (6/43) of those with classical histopathology ($P=0.005$). This finding underscores the prognostic value of histopathology in predicting long-term surgical cure. Furthermore, no association was found between the specific somatic mutation (e.g., *KCNJ5*, *CACNA1D*, *ATP1A1*, *ATP2B3*) identified in 97% of APAs and PA recurrence (**original research publication #9**).

These collective findings suggest that the histopathological architecture of the resected adrenal gland is a dominant factor in both short- and long-term outcomes, necessitating extended postoperative biochemical follow-up for all patients, particularly those with nonclassical adrenal histopathology.

3.5 Summary of Findings

This project established an integrated model linking molecular, metabolic, and histopathological features of APAs and precursor lesions.

(i) *ABCC3* was identified as a specific marker of *CYP11B2*-negative ZG cells that provides a means to distinguish normal adrenal tissue from pathology. Its inverse relationship with *CYP11B2* enabled precise spatial mapping of the early transition from quiescent zG (*ABCC3*-high/*CYP11B2*-low) to emerging APMs or APAs (*ABCC3*-low/*CYP11B2*-high), thereby elucidating the earliest stages of tumour initiation.

(ii) Ferroptosis and oxidative stress were identified as central processes in APA biology. To sustain uncontrolled hormone production and growth, APA cells undergo extensive metabolic reprogramming towards lipid metabolism and glycolysis, reducing lipid peroxidation and enhancing ferroptosis resistance. The anti-ferroptotic factor *BEX1*, markedly upregulated in micro-APAs, confers protection against oxidative stress and supports tumour cell survival.

(iii) Distinct redox and metabolic adaptations were found to be genotype-dependent. *KCNJ5*-wild-type APAs displayed a pro-oxidant, ZG-like phenotype promoting selection for stress-resistant cells, whereas *KCNJ5*-mutant APAs adopted an antioxidant, lipid-rich, zona fasciculata-like programme. The transcription factor *EGR1* acts as a key regulator at this interface, linking oxidative stress to suppression of *CYP11B2* and coordinating redox balance with hormonal regulation and cell viability.

(iv) Novel regulatory mechanisms for aldosterone production were defined. *ATP2A3* functions as a positive regulator of *CYP11B2* expression and aldosterone synthesis through calcium handling, while *TSPAN12* acts as a negative regulator inversely associated with aldosterone output. *EGR1* integrates oxidative stress responses within this network, repressing *CYP11B2* while promoting redox imbalance. Although *ABCC3* lies outside this regulatory axis, it provides a useful histological marker distinguishing ZG from aldosterone-producing tissue.

(v) Integration of molecular findings with clinical outcomes demonstrated that histopathology is a prominent predictor of outcome. Nonclassical histopathological patterns, such as multinodular or diffuse hyperplasia, were associated with higher risk of biochemical recurrence compared with classical solitary APAs, whereas genotype did not independently predict recurrence in available cohorts. These findings highlight histopathology as a determinant of postoperative outcomes and underscore the need for extended follow-up to optimise long-term management of primary aldosteronism.

3.6 Translational impact and resources

This work improved diagnostic precision, identified mechanistic targets, and refined clinical management in primary aldosteronism. *ABCC3* was established as a marker distinguishing normal ZG from aldosterone-producing lesions, enabling more accurate histopathological assessment and targeted molecular testing. The study outlined regulatory pathways involving *ATP2A3*, *TSPAN12*, and the redox-responsive factor *EGR1*, revealing opportunities for modulating aldosterone synthesis and oxidative stress responses. The involvement of ferroptosis-related mechanisms suggests potential relevance of established redox regulators, such as *GPX4*, for future therapeutic exploration. Genotype-specific metabolic differences between *KCNJ5*-mutant and wild-type tumours highlight the potential for stratified treatment strategies. Clinically, the findings support extended biochemical follow-up after adrenalectomy,

especially for patients with nonclassical histopathology. The integrated adrenal spatial atlas and associated gene data provide a lasting resource for future research into adrenal physiology and disease.

3.7 Conclusions

This project established an integrated molecular and pathological approach for understanding tumourigenesis in APAs and related lesions. Through combined genomic, transcriptomic, spatial and functional analyses, key regulators of aldosterone synthesis and adrenal cell survival were defined, including *ATP2A3*, *TSPAN12*, *EGR1* and *BEX1*. These findings revealed how calcium signalling, redox balance and ferroptotic resistance interact to sustain dysregulated hormone production and cellular viability. Spatial multi-omics analyses identified precursor APA-like subpopulations within normal adrenal tissue, supporting a stepwise model of tumour development. The discovery of *ABCC3* as a marker distinguishing normal ZG from aldosterone-producing tissue can lead to improved diagnostic precision, while integrated clinical analyses confirmed histopathology as a predictor of postoperative outcomes. Collectively, the results provide new mechanistic insight into APA biology, establish tools for refined diagnosis and highlight potential targets for stratified therapeutic approaches in PA.

4 Published Project Results

4.1 Category A - Original Research Publications (with grant support acknowledged)

1. Gong S, Tetti M, Kemter E, Peitzsch M, Mulatero P, Bidlingmaier M, Eisenhofer G, Wolf E, **Reincke M, Williams TA**. *TSPAN12* (Tetraspanin 12) is a novel negative regulator of aldosterone production in adrenal physiology and aldosterone-producing adenomas. *Hypertension* 2023 Feb;80(2):440-450. doi: 10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.122.19783.
2. Yang Y, Tetti M, Vohra T, Adolf C, Seissler J, Hristov M, Belavgeni A, Bidlingmaier M, Linkermann A, Mulatero P, Beuschlein F, **Reincke M, Williams TA**. *BEX1* is differentially expressed in aldosterone-producing adenomas and protects human adrenocortical cells from ferroptosis. *Hypertension* 2021;77(5):1647-1658. doi: 10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.120.16774.
3. Sun Z, Kemter E, Pang Y, Bidlingmaier M, Wolf E, **Reincke M, Williams TA**. *ATP2A3* in primary aldosteronism: machine learning-based discovery and functional validation. *Hypertension* 2025 Feb;82(2):319-332. doi: 10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.124.23817.
4. Pang Y, Gong S, Tetti M, Sun Z, Mir-Bashiri S, Bidlingmaier M, Knösel T, Wolf E, **Reincke M, Kemter E, Williams TA**. *EGR1* regulates oxidative stress and aldosterone production in adrenal cells and aldosterone-producing adenomas. *Redox Biol.* 2025 Jan 15;80:103498. doi: 10.1016/j.redox.2025.103498.
5. Pang Y, Mir-Bashiri S, Sun Z, Yang Y, Castellano I, Knösel T, **Reincke M, Williams TA**. *ABCC3* Is a Differential Marker of CYP11B2-Negative Zona Glomerulosa Cells in Human Adrenal Cortex. *Endocr Pathol.* 2025 May 7;36(1):17. doi: 10.1007/s12022-025-09862-3.
6. Gong S, Sun N, Meyer LS, Tetti M, Koupourtidou C, Krebs S, Masserdotti G, Blum H, Rainey WE, **Reincke M, Walch A, Williams TA**. Primary aldosteronism: spatial multiomics mapping

of genotype-dependent heterogeneity and tumor expansion of aldosterone-producing adenomas. *Hypertension* 2023 Jul;80(7):1555-1567.
doi: 10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.123.20921.

7. Gong S, Tetti M, **Reincke M, Williams TA**. Primary aldosteronism: metabolic reprogramming and the pathogenesis of aldosterone-producing adenomas. *Cancers* 2021;13(15):3716. doi: 10.3390/cancers13153716.

8. Meyer LS, Handgriff L, Lim JS, Udager AM, Kinker I, Ladurner R, Wildgruber M, Knösel T, Bidlingmaier M, Rainey WE, **Reincke M, Williams TA**. Single-center prospective cohort study on the histopathology, genotype, and postsurgical outcomes of patients with primary aldosteronism. *Hypertension* 2021 Sep;78(3):738-746.
doi: 10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.121.17348.

9. Tetti M, Brüdgam D, Burrello J, Udager AM, Riester A, Knösel T, Beuschlein F, Rainey WE, **Reincke M, Williams TA**. Unilateral primary aldosteronism: long-term disease recurrence after adrenalectomy. *Hypertension* 2024 Apr;81(4):936-945.
doi: 10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.123.22281.

Review Manuscripts (with grant support acknowledged)

1. **Reincke M, Bancos I, Mulatero P, Scholl UI, Stowasser M, Williams TA**. Diagnosis and treatment of primary aldosteronism. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol.* 2021;9(12):876-892.
doi: 10.1016/S2213-8587(21)00210-2.

2. **Williams TA, Reincke M**. Pathophysiology and histopathology of primary aldosteronism. *Trends Endocrinol Metab.* 2022;33(1):36-49. doi: 10.1016/j.tem.2021.10.002.

3. Tetti M, Gong S, Veglio F, **Reincke M, Williams TA**. Primary aldosteronism: Pathophysiological mechanisms of cell death and proliferation. *Front Endocrinol.* 2022;13:934326. doi: 10.3389/fendo.2022.934326.

4. **Williams TA, Constantinescu G, Pamporaki C**. Biomarkers for subtype stratification in primary aldosteronism: current and future perspectives. *Eur J Endocrinol.* 2025; Oct 23:lvaf218. doi: 10.1093/ejendo/lvaf218.

4.2 Category B – Any other form of published results None

4.3 Patents (applied for and granted) None